

Schiff base macrocyclic ligand derived from thiosemicarbazone with their spectroscopic and antimicrobial studies

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Abstract : Complexes of Mn^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Pd^{II} , Cu^{II} of general composition $M(L)Cl_2$ and $Pt(L)Cl_4$ with a novel azamacrocyclic ligand viz. 1,3,4,8,9,11-hexaaza-5,7,12,14-tetraphenyl-2,10-dithiocyclo tetradecane, (L) have been synthesized and characterized by elemental analysis, molar conductance, magnetic susceptibility, mass, 1H NMR, IR and UV-Vis spectral studies.

On the basis of these spectral studies an octahedral geometry has been assigned for Mn^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Pt^{IV} complexes, square planar and tetragonal geometry for Pd^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes respectively. The ligand and its metal complexes have been screened *in vitro* against some species of bacteria and plant pathogenic fungi.

Keywords : Macrocyclic ligand, characterization, antifungal, antibacterial activities.

Introduction

The interest in exploring metal ion complexes with macrocyclic ligands has been continuously increasing owing to their structures and potential applications¹⁻¹¹. The chemistry of synthetic macrocyclic complexes is also of great importance due to their use as dyes and pigments, MRI contrast agents and models for naturally occurring macrocycles¹². Schiff base macrocycles were among the first artificial metal macrocyclic complexes to be synthesized¹³. Schiff base macrocyclic ligands were studied widely due to their selective chelation to certain metal ions and coordinating properties of counter ions¹⁴⁻¹⁶. Recent studies on macrocyclic complexes containing mixed nitrogen, sulphur, and/or oxygen donor atoms¹⁷⁻²⁵ show that it is the active area of research. Lindoy^{26,27} and co-workers were reported elegant studies on ligand design and metal ion recognition of macrocyclic complexes. Macrocyclic complexes of transition metal ions, specially those of palladium and platinum were found to have important biological activities. In the present paper, we report the synthesis, spectral characterization and biological screening of Mn^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Pd^{II} , Pt^{IV} and Cu^{II} complexes with a novel azamacrocyclic ligand viz. 1,3,4,8,9,11-hexaaza-5,7,12,14-tetraphenyl-2,10-dithiocyclo tetradecane, (L) Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Preparation and structure of the ligand (L).

Results and discussion

A systematic study of the reactions of metal chlorides with ligand (L) can be represented by eqs. (1) and (2).

where $M = Mn^{II}$, Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II}

On the basis of elemental analysis, the complexes were assigned to possess the composition as shown in Table 1. The molar conductance measurement of the Mn^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes in DMSO solution corresponds to the nonelectrolytic nature²⁸ and therefore these complexes may be formulated as $[M(L)Cl_2]$ [where $M = Mn^{II}$, Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II}]. However complexes of Pd^{II} and Pt^{IV} show molar conductance corresponding to 1 : 2 electro-

lytes and thus these complexes may be formulated as $[\text{Pd}(\text{L})\text{Cl}_2]$ and $[\text{Pt}(\text{L})\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl}_2$.

The electron impact mass spectrum of ligand (L) confirms the proposed formula by showing molecular ion peak at m/z 558 amu (Fig. 2) corresponding to the macrocyclic moiety $[\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{24}\text{N}_4\text{S}_2]$. The mass spectra of complexes confirmed the proposed formulae by showing the molecular ion peak at m/z 682, 688, 686, 734, 692 amu corresponding to macrocyclic species $[\text{Mn}(\text{L})\text{Cl}_2]$, $[\text{Co}(\text{L})\text{Cl}_2]$, $[\text{Ni}(\text{L})\text{Cl}_2]$, $[\text{Pd}(\text{L})\text{Cl}_2]$ and $[\text{Cu}(\text{L})\text{Cl}_2]$ respectively.

Fig. 2. Electron impact mass spectrum of the ligand (L).

The IR spectrum of ligand (L) does not show any band corresponding to a free primary diamine and keto

group. The main characteristic band corresponding to $>\text{C}=\text{N}$ is appeared at 1595 cm^{-1} in the free ligand. This confirms that the reaction between primary amine group, $-\text{NH}_2$ of diamine and carbonyl group, $>\text{C}=\text{O}$ of diketone has occurred and water molecules has been eliminated. A band appeared at *ca.* 835 cm^{-1} corresponding to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{S})$ in the IR spectrum of ligand does not shift on complexation it shows that $\nu(\text{C}=\text{S})$ group is not taking part in coordination. On the other hand, the position of band corresponding to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ is shifted to lower side $25\text{--}37\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which indicates that the coordination takes place through the nitrogen atom of the $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ groups.

^1H NMR spectrum of the ligand does not give any signal corresponding to primary amine and alcoholic proton. A signal at δ 1.72–2.24 ppm may be assigned for $(\text{C}-\text{CH}_2-\text{C}, 4\text{H})$ and a strong triplet at δ 7.93–8.44 ppm appeared for $(\text{C}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_5, 20\text{H})$ (Table 4). Another multiplet signal that appears in the region *ca.* 2.32–2.31 ppm may be attributed to the $-\text{NH}$ protons. In the ^1H NMR spectra of Pd^{II} and Pt^{IV} complexes, the red shift of these signals indicate that the coordination is taking place through N-atom. Except palladium and platinum, other complexes are paramagnetic in nature so, ^1H NMR spectrum of other complexes will not be possible.

IR spectra of the complexes : A new band is appeared at $416\text{--}478\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the IR spectra of complexes indicating the formation of $\nu(\text{M}-\text{N})$ bond. It supports the involvement of nitrogen in the coordination²⁹. The bands

Table 1. Molar conductance and elemental analysis data of the complexes

Complex	Molar cond. ($\Omega^{-1}\text{ cm}^2\text{ mol}^{-1}$)	Colour	M.p. ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	Yield (%)	Elemental analysis (%) :			
					Found (Calcd.)			
					M	C	H	N
$[\text{Mn}(\text{L})\text{Cl}_2]$	12.8	Light	242	58	7.97	56.06	3.86	12.35
$\text{MnC}_{32}\text{H}_{26}\text{N}_6\text{S}_2\text{Cl}_2$		brown			(8.04)	(56.14)	(3.80)	(12.28)
$[\text{Co}(\text{L})\text{Cl}_2]$	14.4	Pink	235	65	8.51	55.87	3.83	12.13
$\text{CoC}_{32}\text{H}_{26}\text{N}_6\text{S}_2\text{Cl}_2$					(8.57)	(55.81)	(3.77)	(12.20)
$[\text{Ni}(\text{L})\text{Cl}_2]$	10.5	Bluish	298	64	8.62	55.76	3.70	12.28
$\text{NiC}_{32}\text{H}_{26}\text{N}_6\text{S}_2\text{Cl}_2$		green			(8.57)	(55.81)	(3.77)	(12.20)
$[\text{Pd}(\text{L})\text{Cl}_2]$	246	Green	238	52	14.36	52.32	3.59	11.35
$\text{PdC}_{32}\text{H}_{26}\text{N}_6\text{S}_2\text{Cl}_2$					(14.42)	(52.24)	(3.53)	(11.42)
$[\text{Pt}(\text{L})\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl}_2$	236	Grayish	220	50	23.73	46.55	3.22	10.27
$\text{PtC}_{32}\text{H}_{26}\text{N}_6\text{S}_2\text{Cl}_4$		green			(23.66)	(46.60)	(3.15)	(10.19)
$[\text{Cu}(\text{L})\text{Cl}_2]$	12.5	Green	285	68	9.18	55.54	3.82	12.07
$\text{CuC}_{32}\text{H}_{26}\text{N}_6\text{S}_2\text{Cl}_2$					(9.24)	(55.49)	(3.75)	(12.13)

Table 2. Magnetic moments and electronic spectral data of the complexes

Complex	μ_{eff} (B.M.)	λ_{max} (cm^{-1})
[Mn(L)Cl ₂]	5.84	18621, 22980, 27512, 36250
[Co(L)Cl ₂]	5.06	9685, 14838, 18621
[Ni(L)Cl ₂]	3.02	10183, 18621, 27624
[Pd(L)]Cl ₂	Diamagnetic	22042, 26928, 37485
[Pt(L)Cl ₂]Cl ₂	Diamagnetic	27508, 37921
[Cu(L)Cl ₂]	1.98	11182, 18621, 27762

spectrum of Ni^{II} complex, as shown in Fig. 3, display three bands at 10183, 18621 and 27624 cm^{-1} assignable to ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$ (ν_1), ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ (ν_2) and ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ (ν_3) transitions respectively (Table 2). Thus, Ni^{II} complex possess octahedral geometry.

Palladium(II) and platinum(IV) : Pd^{II} and Pt^{IV} complexes are diamagnetic as expected for a low spin d^8 and d^6 systems. The electronic spectrum of Pd^{II} complex displays two bands at 22042 and 26928 cm^{-1} , assigned to

Table 3. Ligand field parameter of the complexes

Complex	Dq (cm^{-1})	B (cm^{-1})	β	C (cm^{-1})	F_4	F_2	h_x	LFSE (kJ mol^{-1})
[Mn(L)Cl ₂]	1862	647	0.82	3302	94.34	1118.7	2.57	-
[Co(L)Cl ₂]	1209	654	0.58	-	-	-	-	115
[Ni(L)Cl ₂]	1018	997	0.95	-	-	-	-	146

Table 4. ¹H NMR spectroscopic data of the ligand and complexes

Compounds	C-CH ₂ -C	C-C ₆ H ₅	-NH
Ligand (L)	2.18 (s)	8.38 (t)	2.30 (m)
[Pd(L)]Cl ₂	2.20 (s)	8.39 (t)	2.42 (m)
[Pt(L)Cl ₂]Cl ₂	2.19 (s)	8.41 (t)	2.45 (m)

Chemical shift (ppm) with multiplicities in parentheses, (s) singlet, (t) triplet, m (multiplet).

at 762 cm^{-1} and 1469 cm^{-1} ^{30,31} are due to the presence of phenyl ring in the macrocycle.

Manganese(II) complex : Mn^{II} complex shows magnetic moment corresponding to five unpaired electrons (Table 2). The electronic spectrum of Mn^{II} complex, displays four weak intensity absorption bands at 18621, 22980, 27512 and 36250 cm^{-1} (Fig. 3). These bands may be assigned to the transitions ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}({}^4G)$, ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4E_g$, ${}^4A_{1g}({}^4G)$ ($10B + 5C$), ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4E_g(4D)$ ($17B + 5C$) and ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}({}^4P)$ ($7B + 7C$), respectively.

Cobalt(II) complex : Magnetic moment of Co^{II} complex corresponds to three unpaired electrons. The electronic spectrum of Co^{II} complex shows three bands at 9685, 14838 and 18621 cm^{-1} (Table 2). These bands may be assigned to the transitions ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$ (ν_1), ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}$ (ν_2) and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ (ν_3), respectively. The position of these bands suggests an octahedral environment around the cobalt(II) ion.

Nickel(II) complex : Ni^{II} complex shows magnetic moment (Table 2) corresponding to two electrons. Electronic

${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1A_{2g}$ and ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1B_{1g}$ transitions respectively and a charge transfer band at 37485 cm^{-1} (Fig. 3). Thus, Pd^{II} complex may possess square planar geometry. The electronic spectra of Pt^{IV} complex displays two absorption bands at 27508 and 37921 cm^{-1} (Table 2). First band may be assigned to ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1T_{1g}$ transition and second band is due to charge transfer. Thus, Pt^{IV} complex may possess octahedral geometry.

Copper(II) complex : The magnetic moment of Cu^{II} complex (Table 2) corresponds to one unpaired electron. The electronic spectrum of Cu^{II} complex, (Fig. 3) displays three bands at 11085, 18621 and 27598 cm^{-1} corresponds to tetragonal geometry, which can be assigned to ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$, ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}$ and ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$ transitions, respectively.

Ligand field parameters : Various ligand field parameters were calculated for the complexes and are listed in Table 3. The value of Dq for Co^{II} complex was calculated from the transition energy ratio diagram using ν_3/ν_2 ratio. The Nephelauxetic parameter $\beta = B(\text{Complex})/B(\text{Free ion})$, where $B(\text{Free ion})$ for Mn^{II} is 786, for Ni^{II} is 1041 and for Co^{II} is 1120 cm^{-1} . The values of β lies in the range 0.58–0.95. The values of β and h_x indicate the appreciable covalent character of metal-ligand σ bond. The graphical information contained in Orgel energy level diagram. Parameter B and C are a linear combination of

Fig. 3. Electronic spectra of the complexes : (a) $[Mn(L)Cl_2]$, (b) $[Co(L)Cl_2]$, (c) $[Ni(L)Cl_2]$, (d) $[Pd(L)Cl_2]$, (e) $[Pt(L)Cl_2]Cl_2$, (f) $[Cu(L)Cl_2]$.

certain Coloumb's exchange internal and are generally treated as empirical parameters obtained from the spectra of free ions. For Mn^{II} complex the values of B and C are calculated from the second transition because this transition is free from the crystal field splitting and depend on B and C parameters. Slater Condon-Shortly parameters F_2 and F_4 are related to Racah parameter B and C as : $B = F_2 - 5F_4$ and $C = 35F_4$.

Antimicrobial study : The ligand (L) and its complexes

were evaluated against different species of fungi and bacteria.

Antifungal activity : The preliminary fungitoxicity screening of the compounds at different concentrations were performed *in vitro* by the Agar Plate Technique³²⁻³⁴. The choosen strains were *Aspergillus niger*, *Aspergillus glaucus* and *Aspergillus flavus* (Table 5). Chlorothalonil was used as commercial fungicide. Appropriate quantities of the compounds were mixed in autoclaved and ade-

Table 5. Antifungal screening data of the ligand (L) and its complexes

Comps.	Fungal inhibition (%) (conc. in $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$)					
	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>		<i>Aspergillus glaucus</i>		<i>Aspergillus flavus</i>	
	125	250	125	250	125	250
L	32	53	18	41	38	54
[Mn(L)Cl ₂]	36	58	29	44	41	59
[Co(L)Cl ₂]	40	62	31	48	49	63
[Ni(L)Cl ₂]	39	62	30	49	49	62
[Pd(L)Cl ₂]	52	77	50	66	60	80
[Pt(L)Cl ₂ Cl ₂]	52	78	52	65	62	81
[Cu(L)Cl ₂]	45	69	40	60	55	75
Chlorothalonil (std)	63	86	68	82	74	90

quately cooled potato dextrose agar medium in order to get concentrations of 125 and 250 ppm. The medium was dispensed into sterilized petriplates. A mycelial discs of 0.5 cm in diameter of test pathogen taken from 7 days old culture with the help of sterilized cork was placed at the centre of the petriplates. These treated petriplates were incubated at 27 °C until fungal growth in the control petriplate was almost complete.

The mycelial growth of fungi (mm) in each petriplate was measured diametrically and growth inhibition (*I*) were calculated by using the formula :

$$I(\%) = \frac{C - T}{C} \times 100$$

[where *C* is the growth of the fungus (mm) in control plate and *T* is the growth of test compounds]. The results are shown in Graph 1.

Antibacterial activity : The antibacterial activity of the ligand and its metal complexes were tested by using Disc Diffusion Method³⁵⁻⁴¹ against *Sarcina lutea* (Gram-positive) and *Staphylococcus aureus* (Gram-negative) (Table 6). Nutrient agar medium was prepared by using peptone, beef extract, NaCl, agar-agar and distilled water. The test compounds in measured quantities were dissolved in DMF to get a concentrations of 125 and 250 ppm 25 mL nutrient agar media (NA) was poured in each petriplate. After solidification 0.1 mL of test bacteria spreads over the medium using a spreader. The disc of Whatmann no. 1 filter paper having the diameter 5.00 mm each containing (1.5 mg cm⁻¹) of compounds were

Graph 1. Antifungal activity (a) at 125 ppm and (b) at 250 ppm.

Table 6. Antibacterial screening data of the ligand (L) and its complexes

Comps.	Diameter (mm) of compounds at concentrations ($\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$)			
	<i>Sarcina lutea</i>		<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	
	125	250	125	250
L	-	10	7	13
[Mn(L)Cl ₂]	8	11	11	15
[Co(L)Cl ₂]	11	15	13	18
[Ni(L)Cl ₂]	15	20	17	22
[Pd(L)Cl ₂]	17	22	21	26
[Pt(L)Cl ₂ Cl ₂]	18	22	22	27
[Cu(L)Cl ₂]	21	26	25	28
Streptomycin (std)	24	28	28	33

placed at 4 equidistant places at a distance of 2 cm from the center in the inoculated petriplates. Streptomycin was used as a standard drug. All determinations were made in duplicate for each of the compounds. Average of two independent readings for each compound was recorded. These petriplates were kept in refrigerator for 24 h for Pre-diffusion. Finally petriplates were incubated for 28 h at 30 °C. The zone of inhibition was calculated in mm carefully. The results are shown in Graph 2.

Graph 2. Antibacterial activity (a) at 125 ppm and (b) at 250 ppm.

The antimicrobial screening data show that the metal chelates exhibit higher inhibitory effects than free ligand. The increased activity of the metal chelates can be explained on the basis of chelation theory⁴².

The ligand and its metal complexes show fungal growth inhibition in the following order :

The bacterial growth inhibitory capacity of the ligand and its metal complexes show the following order :

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade and procured from Sigma-Aldrich. Metal salts were purchased from E. Merck and were used as received.

Synthesis of ligand (L) : The hot ethanolic solution (20 mL) of dibenzoylmethane (4.48 g, 0.02 mol) and hot ethanolic solution (20 mL) of thiosemicarbazide (1.82 g, 0.02 mol) were mixed slowly with constant stirring. This mixture was refluxed at 80 °C for 6 h in presence of few drops of hydrochloric acid. Upon cooling, a solid white precipitate was formed. It was filtered, washed with cold

EtOH and dried under vacuum over P_4O_{10} . (Yield, 60%); m.p. 162 °C. Elemental analysis found (%) C, 68.75; H, 4.72; N, 15.13; calculated for $\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{26}\text{N}_6\text{S}_2$ (atomic mass 558) was C, 68.82; H, 4.66; N, 15.05%.

Synthesis of complexes : The hot ethanolic solution (20 mL) of ligand (0.558 g, 0.001 mol) and hot ethanolic solution (20 mL) of corresponding metal salt (0.001 mol) were mixed together with constant stirring. The mixture was refluxed for 6 to 8 h at 75 °C. Upon cooling a coloured precipitate was formed. It was filtered, washed with cold EtOH and dried under vacuum over P_4O_{10} . The purity of the complexes was checked by thin layer chromatography (TLC).

Physical measurements : Analytical data were obtained with a Carlo-Erba 1106 elemental analyzer. Molar conductance was measured on the ELICO (CM82T) conductivity bridge. Magnetic susceptibility was measured at room temperature on a Gouy balance using $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ as a callibrant. Electron impact mass spectra were recorded on TOF MS ES+ mass spectrometer. ^1H NMR spectra were recorded on Hitachi FT-NMR, model R-600 spectrometer using DMSO as a solvent, chemical shifts are given in ppm relative to tetramethylsilane. IR spectra (CsI) were recorded on a FTIR Spectrum BX-II spectrophotometer. The electronic spectra were recorded in DMSO on Shimadzu UV mini-1240 spectrophotometer. EPR spectra of the complexes were recorded as polycrystalline sample at room temperature on E_4 -EPR spectrometer using the DPPH as the *g*-marker.

Conclusions :

On the basis of present spectral studies the ligand is found to be tetradentate in nature. An octahedral geometry has been assigned for Mn^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Pt^{IV} complexes, square planar geometry for Pd^{II} and tetragonal geometry for Cu^{II} complexes. The antimicrobial screening indicates that the metal chelates show greater inhibitory effect than metal free ligand. It is also proposed that concentration plays a vital role in increasing the degree of inhibition. As the concentration increases, the activity increases.

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